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Towards Mechanical Engineers' Expertise with Problem Based Learning

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ABSTRACT

Working in the Lapland area, the Mechanical Engineers need diversified knowledge. In the area, there exists steel, paper and mining industry and maintenance and design enterprises supporting these industry operations. The demands of the engineer knowledge are not only restricted to mechanical engineering but the engineers also need e.g. social, analytical thinking, problem solving and language skills, and especially how to combine their own knowledge with other specialists.

The curriculum of Mechanical Engineering Education is based on competence and problem-based learning and it was introduced in the autumn 2017. The curriculum consists of the academic year and semester themes and every semester has a CDIO-type semester project course. This article describes the experiences of the curriculum so far and how new teaching contents are integrated in the education. The curriculum permits flexibility to the contents and it can be updated if there are new subjects to be taught e.g. Circular Economy. The curriculum requires collaborative teaching and development of the learning methods and environments. It can be seen that the motivation of the students has increased and the dropouts decreased with this curriculum.

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INTRODUCTION

Lapland University of Applied Sciences has developed the curriculum of education and the competence and problem-based learning curriculum started in the autumn 2017. The curriculum of Mechanical Engineering consists of semester projects and various study modules reflecting the competences. The names of these projects and study modules are inspiring and modern and try to illustrate better the theme of the academic year to the students. In this curriculum the teachers plan, check, guide and assess the courses together and are more like counsellors in the students' learning processes. Competency-based curriculum considers the students more as individuals than as groups and this requires the students to be more active in their learning process.

The professional growth of the mechanical engineers proceeds gradually from the first academic year to the last year in every academic year and semester themes. The problem-based learning project is in the centre of every semester theme and the contents of the different study modules are integrated into the content of the semester project. The curriculum permits flexibility to the contents and it can be updated if there are new subjects from the engineering field to be taught for the students. Especially for young students the professional field of the studies may not be so well known so it is important to familiarize them with the Mechanical Engineering field. It is also very important to support the students to learn to know each other well so they can work in groups and smaller teams. With these actions, the students' motivation to study can increase and they complete their studies as planned.

1 DEVELOPING THE CURRICULUM

The curricula of Lapland University of Applied Sciences (later LUAS) are based on competence and problem-based learning (later PBL). The aim of the problem-based learning is to increase creativity and communality in the students' learning processes. The individual students study as active team members resolving learning problems where the alternative proposition of the solutions expand the students' individual knowledge. In that way, the learning is work-oriented learning. The essential themes are interaction and co-operation between the students, communal learning, the guidance of learning, invocation of the group dynamics in the learning process and developing evaluation. Learning by the PBL method is widely used in Engineering Education. The target of the LUAS curriculum is to confirm a creative and learner-centred culture of learning. Fragmentary courses are integrated into larger modules and the students together process the phenomena and problems of the working life. (Kangastie, Mastosaari, 2016)

The teaching with these competence and problem-based curricula started in the autumn 2017. The development process of the curriculum was presented at SEFI Conference Autumn 2017. Most of the courses are taught by "teacher teams" that mainly consist of two to four teachers. Every teacher teaches different subjects so the team teachers plan, teach and assess the pedagogic learning process together. The individual teachers gain better overview of the education and have an insight into different subjects. Therefore, the integration between different subjects deepens. The role of the teacher is changed when the curricula is competence and problem-based.

The teacher is more like a counsellor, and instead of giving a lecture, the teacher introduces a problem and the students search for information and try to solve the problem. Therefore, information retrieval is essential in the learning process. The competence-based curriculum considers the students more as individuals than as groups and it also requires the students to be more active in their learning processes. (Kantanen, Ruottu, 2017)

Bachelor of Engineering studies take four years to complete containing 240 ECTS credits. The structure of the Mechanical Engineering curriculum consists of Basic and Professional studies 180 ECTS (Basic Studies (50 ECTS) and Professional Studies (130 ECTS)), Elective Studies 15 ECTS, Practical Training 30 ECTS and Thesis 15 ECTS. The professional growth of the Mechanical Engineer proceeds gradually from the first academic year to the last academic year with different semester themes. The same curriculum is applied both in full time and part time education, only some of the vocational subject studies are compensated with practical training e.g. the part time students do not have the first-year semester projects in their curriculum. The students in part-time education study in the evenings and on Saturdays, and so the number of contact lessons is smaller. The teaching methods can consist e.g. of flipped classroom, simulation, online teaching and independent studies.

In the department of Mechanical Engineering, the new curriculum consists of the academic year and semester themes. The academic year themes are *Learning about Work of Mechanical Engineers*, *Engineer's Toolbox*, *Creative Engineers* and *Pre-Engineers*. The learning and/or problem-based CDIO-type semester project is in the centre of every semester theme and all the other courses support this project course. CDIO organization is a worldwide network to develop and reform the Engineering Education (<http://cdio.org/about>). The letters CDIO stand for Conceiving - Designing – Implementing – Operating and so is the framework of the curricula planning and outcome-based assessment. The CDIO Initiative developed 12 standards that describe the programs giving educational program reform and assessment; and this framework can be used for continuous development and improvement in educational institutions. Each institution can apply the CDIO standards, because there is no formal certification as a CDIO program. The standards include program philosophy, curriculum development, design-build experiences and workspaces, new methods of teaching and learning, faculty development and assessment and evaluation. Thus, these all serve as good guidelines for educational development and improvement. The names of the academic years, semester projects and study modules in the curriculum of the Mechanical Engineering illustrate better the theme of the academic year to the students. The professional growth of the mechanical engineers proceeds gradually from the first academic year to the last year of their education having different semester themes every academic year supporting the student's professional growth.

2 SEMESTER THEME PROJECTS IN MECHANICAL ENGINEERING EDUCATION

The learning and problem-based project is in the center of every semester theme. The contents of the different study modules are integrated into the content of the semester project. The competence of the student is based on these semester themes. (Kantanen, Ruottu, 2017)

In the first academic year, the field of Mechanical Engineering becomes familiar to the students and they practice basic subjects of Mechanical Engineering combined with natural science, language and social skill studies. The content of the first Academic Semester is illustrated in table 1.

Table 1. The content of the first Academic Year.

1. Academic Year					
Academic Year Theme	Semester Theme	Study Module	Extent	Responsible Teacher	Other Teachers
Learning about Work of Mechanical Engineers	On the Way to Becoming an Engineer	Project: Familiarization with Arctic Working Environment	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Perspective on Work of Engineers	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Natural Sciences of Engineers	5	N.N.	D.D.
		Tools and Software of Learning	5	N.N.	E.E.
		The basic of Technical Design	5	N.N.	
		Basics of Industrial Engineering	5	N.N.	F.F.
	Language of Engineers	Project: How to Use the Tools of Engineers	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Tools of Mathematics and Physics	5	N.N.	G.G.
		Basic of Mechanical Engineering	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Manufacturing Processes and Material Science	5	N.N.	
		Basics of Technical Mechanics	5	N.N.	
		Projects and Workshops	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B.

First year’s semester projects are in the autumn “On the way to Becoming an Engineer” and in the spring “Language of the Engineers”. In the autumn projects, the students are familiarized with different kinds of industries of the Lapland region. The semester project is culminated with a fair where the students introduce their semester project results, and the companies introduce activities and practical training possibilities for the students. At the fair the student teams also compete, the participants of the fair can vote which group has the best poster and the performance. In the spring project the students build spaghetti bridges in smaller teams and for that the students need competence e.g. in design and technical mechanics. The results are presented in the topical themed seminar (project day) which is arranged for the co-operative companies and other important partners of the LUAS. In this seminar, the student teams also compete which team has the greatest bridge. The participants of the fair vote for the greatest bridge.

In the second academic year, the basic tools of the Mechanical Engineering become more familiar and the students learn how to apply all the knowledge they have

achieved. The students can also work on the projects and they can apply different kinds of problem-based methods. The content of the second Academic Semester is illustrated in table 2.

Table 2. The content of the second Academic Year.

2. Academic Year					
Academic Year Theme	Semester Theme	Study Module	Extent	Responsible Teacher	Other Teachers
Engineers toolbox	Pouch the toolbox	Project: Product development	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Mathematics of the Engineers	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		CAD as a tool	5	N.N.	D.D.
		Technical mechanics	5	N.N.	E.E.
		Automation solutions	5	N.N.	F.F.
		Practical training 1	5	N.N.	F.F.
	Solving practical problems	Project: Prototype	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		3D design of the product	5	N.N.	G.G.
		Energy and environment	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B., C.C.
		Material properties	5	N.N.	C.C.
		Effective production environment	5	N.N.	A.A., B.B.
		Application of the physics	5	N.N.	A.A.

The second year’s autumn project is a product development and the theme of the project is to design a table fan in a smaller group. In the spring project, these student groups manufacture prototypes of these table fans. The second year’s projects follow CDIO project steps and the students need competence in material science, manufacturing processes, CAD design, energy technologies. The students can manufacture the parts of the table fans with 3D printing or machining steel. The table fans are presented in the semester project day together with the first-year students’ spaghetti bridges.

The third year’s semester projects are company-based and real working life problems and the first projects with this curriculum will be started in the autumn 2019. There are three different kinds of alternative professional study options in the Mechanical Engineering education curriculum and the students choose one of them in the third academic year. These alternative professional studies are: Industrial Professional, Product Development Professional and Mining Professional. All these alternative professional studies contain semester projects, mandatory courses and optional courses. In the region of Lapland, there are steel, paper, energy, mining, design and engineering workshop companies so the subjects of the projects can vary a lot and the student can participate in a project which best suits for his/her career plans. The students can choose some of the semesters study modules, which are integrated into the content of the semester project and best support the competence of the students. The curriculum is flexible and the content of the semester study modules can be modified if there are some special competence needs from the industry. For example,

the theme Circular Economy was very important in the industry and thus current in the engineering education. Therefore, in the Mechanical Engineering education, these themes were included in the different professional subjects, as a cross section theme and it did not demand any changes in the curriculum and all the students gain sufficient knowledge about the current themes. In the last academic year, the students deepen the Mechanical Engineering competence and at the end of the year they will graduate.

2.1 Learning about Work of Mechanical Engineers: the first year semester projects

Especially for the young students the professional field of the studies may not be so familiar and if the students they do not recognize and understand that, the motivation for the studies may not be high and they can possible drop out their studies. It is also very important to support that the students get to know each other well so they can work as group and smaller teams. It is well known that grouping of the students increases the commitment to the studies which also increases the motivation to the studies. To reinforce grouping, both the young and the adult students make together first excursion at the beginning of the studies to the old mill and sawmill museum Kukkolaforsen which is located quite near to our school, at the shore of the Tornio River in Sweden, figure 1.

Fig. 1. The young and adult students familiarize themselves with the old sawmill.

In the curriculum of Mechanical Engineering, there are many studies where the engineering work and working environments are demonstrated in the basic and professional studies. In the autumn semester projects, the students are familiarized with different kinds of industries of the Lapland region and they also visit different companies. The semester project is culminated in the fair where the students introduce their semester project results. One of the main goals of the semester projects is to arrange the fair where different companies of the Lapland region can introduce their activities and practical training possibilities for the students. The students make posters on a selected industry for the fair and present them at the fair. The students must also prepare an elevator pitch of their subject. It is a very important competence for the

future engineers to sell his/her own competence and with these different training the students can learn and reinforce these skills. At the fair, the student teams also compete which group has the best poster and the performance and the participants of the fair can vote their own favorite group, figure 2.

Fig. 2. The company desks at the fair (left) and the winner of the student projects (right).

In the spring project, the students build spaghetti bridges in smaller teams and the results are presented in the project day, which is also, a topical themed seminar arranged for the co-operative companies and other important partners of the LUAS. In this seminar, the student teams also compete, and the participants of the fair can vote which group has the greatest bridge, figure 3.

Fig. 3. Learning basics of teamwork on the lessons and semester day.

2.2 Engineer's Toolbox: second year project

The autumn semester theme of the second year is Engineer's Toolbox containing the following supporting courses Engineer's Mathematics, CAD as a Tool, Technical/Engineering Mechanics, Automation Solutions. These courses give the students tools for the semester project Production Development. The subject of the project is given by the teachers and in the academic year 2018-2019 it was a table fan. In this project, the students learn about product development process and its different sections by teamwork. In addition, the students strengthen their team working and documentation skills. Based on the teachers' evaluation of the students' participation in and contribution to working in teams the previous year. Additionally, the skills of the students were taken into account to balance the team's skills as much as possible. In this academic year, the exchange students participated in the semester and due to this teaching on the courses was in English and the students got a lot internationalization at home. This course is strongly linked to the C (Conceive) and D (Design) phases of the CDIO model that is widely used in technology. The students participate in the design process, CAD labs, material selection and planning the design and functions of the product. They also draw up technical drawings and charts and evaluate the expenses and cost-effectiveness of the product.

The spring semester project continues the semester project of the autumn term and focuses on the final I (Implementation) and O (Operate) phases of the CDIO model. During the spring semester, the students complete the design and prepare a prototype of the product and the students need competence e.g. in material science, 3D design, effective production methods (Lean, 5S), energy technologies. The students can manufacture the parts of the table fans with 3D printing or machining steel and they can manufacture the parts of the fans at school or at home or at work. They also pay attention to the life cycle of the product and make improvements in the design. Additionally, they also consider operation and maintenance. Furthermore, they learn how to productize products and services. The solutions of the table fans by the different student teams were very different, and they presented the project progress with slide shows and the fans were on display in the semester project day together with the first-year student's spaghetti bridges, figure 4.

Fig. 4. The winning table ventilator solution by the adult student team (left) and the solutions of the different ventilators by the young students (right).

The third year's academic year theme is *Creative Engineers*. The third year's semester projects continue through the whole academic year and they are company-based real working life problems. The students have practised teamwork in the first and second academic years and they have different kind of professional competence. These skills are needed when solving the problems together. Solving real working life problems together helps the students to solve problems later at work. The last, fourth year's academic theme is *Pre-Engineers*. In that academic year, the students start their theses which are company-based subjects in Mechanical Engineering. In the thesis, the student solves real working life problems alone with guidance by the counsellors, but it is important that they have practised problem solving in the earlier studies.

3 THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CURRICULUM, DOES IT HAVE AN INFLUENCE ON THE MOTIVATION OF THE STUDENTS?

One of the goals for the curriculum development is to influence the student's motivation to study and reduce possible dropouts. In addition, working life and job descriptions are changing quite rapidly, the educators need to consider what kind of competence is needed in working life in the future. In engineering education, it is necessary to teach natural sciences and selected subjects of the technical field but also social skills, analytical thinking skills, problem solving skills, language skills are considered important in working life. The students must know how they learn and adopt new and how they can combine their own knowledge with other students.

The Mechanical Engineering department is quite a small unit in the LUAS, other engineering departments are Electrical and Automation Engineering, Civil Engineering, Information Technology, Land Survey Engineering and Forestry Engineering. The applicants can apply for fulltime or part-time education and there are about 50 starting places in Mechanical Engineering education. The first year of the studies is very critical and usually if the student is going to break the studies, it usually is going to happen after the first year.

It is evident that the dropouts of the studies has reduced some with new curriculum. Generally, the students drop out their studies after the first or second year of the studies. Earlier with old curriculum about 10-20 % of the young students (full time students) dropped out the studies. The percent of the dropouts of the part time students (adult students) was even higher but usually there are more elements which affect the motivation of the studies (lack of time, family, job and other competing elements). It has been seen that these dropouts have decreased but there is only two-year experience and evidence of this curriculum. It is also important that the studies proceed as planned in the curriculum and it has proven that this factor has improved with this competence and problem-based curriculum. The semester themed projects and study modules may reinforce the interest of the students in the Mechanical Engineering field and they find diverse job opportunities in the field. There has been many other development actions in the education with development of the curriculum e.g. development of the learning environments. This contains development of the virtual learning environment and the laboratory environment. In virtual learning environment, the clarity of the layouts and the evaluation tools of the students' learning process have improved and developed. In Mechanical Engineering Education there is

an investment project going on where brand new laboratory facilities are being built for the educational purposes. The new laboratory is called “Intelligence workshop” that will be modern with diverse equipment for laboratory work (industry 4.0). Student counselling is being developed, and with this new curriculum the teachers are more like counsellors in the students’ learning processes. Further reviews should be made to find out what the main reasons are that influence the motivation of the students and reduce dropouts.

4 SUMMARY

The new problem-based curriculum has changed the roles of the teachers as well the students. It has deepened the teachers’ cooperation and the students have learned working life skills along with their engineering studies and taken more responsibility of their studies. The different courses are integrated into the projects to give an overall insight into the contents of the semester theme. This is also seen in the virtual Moodle environment where all the semester courses are presented in the same course environment as interleaves.

In the future, the challenge is to make Mechanical Engineering more popular for the candidates. The population of the Lapland is decreasing and still there are quite a lot job opportunities for engineers in the area. Furthermore, when the students start the education it is important that their interest in the studies is high and they perform their studies as planned. The content of the education must be attractive, diverse and ahead of time. The challenges in lifelong learning and development of the competences challenge the educators to develop the contents of the degree programs. In the future, more short time updating training courses are needed and diverse implementation of the education. This challenges the educators to acknowledge and recognize the former competence of the students even better.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kangastie, H, Mastosaari, P, (2016), Competence- and Problem-based Learning at Lapland University of Applied Sciences, Publications of Lapland UAS, Publications Series C. Study Material 6/2016.
- [2] Kantanen, M-S, Ruottu, M. (2017), Challenges in the Curriculum Development, Steps to the Collaborative Teaching, 45th SEFI Conference, 18-21 September 2017, Azores, Portugal
- [3] CDIO INITIATIVE, Implementing CDIO your institutions, standards, referred 28.4.2019, <http://cdio.org/about>